

Information Communication Technology (ICT) and Women Students in Higher Educational Institutions in Tirunelveli

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:
Radha, B., and R.
Nivetha. "Information
Communication
Technology (ICT) and
Women Students in
Higher Educational
Institutions in
Tirunelveli." *Shanlax
International Journal
of Arts, Science and
Humanities*, vol. 6,
no. S1, 2019, pp. 5–7.

DOI:
[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2551314](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2551314)

Dr.B.Radha

*Assistant Professor, Department of Communication
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abisekapatti, Tirunelveli*

R.Nivetha

*Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Communication
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abisekapatti, Tirunelveli*

Abstract

In today's modern era, people all over the world use Internet through digital gadgets like smart phones, laptops, tablets etc. Especially women use Internet for many purposes like entertainment, shopping, chatting with friends and family those who are nearby or abroad. The availability of online services or apps has made lives easy by single click from their place wherever they are. Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) enable many women who have access to internet exchange information and views more quickly and widely with others. On the other hand, the development of ICTs comes with the new computer related crimes known as cyber crimes where women become victims of cyber crimes, like cyber-stalking, bullying, cheating, morphing, pornography, threats or harassments via email, whatsapp messages, etc. Cyber-crime is a global phenomenon and women are the main targets of this new form of crime. Women students are the most vulnerable ones owing to their access of ICTs in educational institutions. Most of the women students are not aware of the nature of the crimes and security measures. This paper tries to find out the ICT usage patterns, level of awareness on cybercrimes, the nature of crimes prevalent among women students in higher educational institutions and to know whether women students have been victims of cybercrime in the process of access of Internet or any other forms of electronic devices.

Keywords: Cybercrime, Women Students, ICTs, Higher Educational Institutions, Usage Patterns.

Introduction

In current scenario, as technology develops cyber crime also increases very rapidly. Cyber crime is an unlawful act which means crime against the law. Computer crime or cyber crime is a criminal activity committed via Internet. Nowadays, smart phones play a major role in accessing the Internet. Most of the cyber crimes are targeted against women to harm them physically and psychologically using telecommunication networks such as Internet and mobile phones. Crimes can be done to individuals through Bluetooth, SMS and MMS of Mobile Phones. Cyber crimes may also threaten persons

financial health. There are different types of crime namely cyber stalking, cyber bullying, cyber pornography, cyber terrorism etc., So it is necessary for each and every person to be aware of cyber crimes while using online. The nature of ICTs does not have any rigid regulations, but it still faces challenges regarding principles of criminal laws. This paper is to study the usages patterns of ICT, especially the nature of crimes among women in Tirunelveli city. The study at the initial stage uses survey method and direct distribution of questionnaires to the Respondents along with face-to-face interactions.

Background of the Study

India, users of its Internet base is the second largest after China, will remain the fastest growing market, according to 'The Future of Internet in India' report by NASSCOM and Akamai Technologies. The report said that 75% of new internet users in India will come from rural areas. An overwhelming majority (75%) of new users will consume data in local languages, it said. "India's Internet consumption has already exceeded the US to become number two globally... By 2020, the internet is expected to penetrate deeper in hinterlands of the country, helping create more opportunities for everyone,". President of NASSCOM Dr.R.Chandrashekhar said. (source: ETCIO.com An initiative of The Economic Times).

Need and Significance of the Study

Nowadays Internet has changed the lifestyle of people. Our days come across with some kind of crime known as cyber crimes. Most of the cyber crime offenders are mainly Youth and College Students. It is essential to find out the awareness level of cyber crime among women students.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the current study are as follows:

1. To find out the ICT usage patterns
2. To understand the level of awareness on Cybercrimes
3. To analyze the nature of crimes prevalent among women students in Higher Educational Institutions
4. To know whether women students have been victims of cybercrime in the process of access of Internet or any other forms of electronic devices.

Methodology

Survey method is used in this study. Survey is a method used to collect data from or samples taken for the Research. Surveys can be conducted in different methods such as Telephone, Email etc. In this paper, questionnaires are used to collect data from the samples. A sample of 97 Respondents is taken for the study. The sample was chosen using purposive sampling, which is also known as selective or subjective sampling in which the Researcher chose the own Respondents from the population for their study as women students. Women face many challenges in India rather than other countries. The samples are drawn from different Colleges in Tirunelveli, were initially taken as purposive sampling for this study.

Findings and Interpretations of the Study

The pilot study is used to find the usage patterns of ICT among women in Tirunelveli city.

Usage Patterns of Internet

Among 97 Respondents, 71% fall under the age group between 17 and 21 the use Internet, 73% of the Respondents use smart phone for accessing Internet. 51% of the Respondents access Internet

from their Institutions, 47% of them access Internet from their home. 34% of the Respondents use Internet for communication as well as entertainment purpose and the rest 28% use it for education purpose. 66% of the Respondents spent 1-2 hours on using Internet per day. 82% of the Respondents use Internet daily. 39% of the Respondents use all the modes such as Gmail, Facebook, Twitter, 35% use only whatsapp. 38% of the women Respondents inform their critical situation regarding cybercrime to their family members, 25% of them just ignore it.

Problem Faced due the usage of Internet

Among 97 Respondents, 42% of them face difficulties in lack of time, 48% have restrictions from their homes, 38% of the Respondents have difficulties in lack of money, 70% have abuse fear, 42% thinks studies get affected, 59% feels Internet as an addiction, 78% have technical difficulties, 34% have social pressure that Internet users are not good.

Awareness Level of Cybercrime

Among 97 Respondents, 21% of women students have experienced cyber stalking, 12% have received obscene videos and pics, 51% received unwanted messages via email, 11% come across cyber extortion, 5% faced phising, 12% faced derogatory comments based on their religion, 15% faced a problem of Identity theft.

Conclusion

Findings of the study clearly shows that most of the women Respondents access Internet through smart phones from their institutions. Prominent use of Internet is for communication and entertainment. Many of them use Internet daily. Only very a few women Respondents have awareness about cybercrime.

References

- Aloul, Fadi A. "The need for Effective Information Security Awareness". *Advances in Information Technology*. 2012.
- Dr Jane Leclair, Dr Lifang Shih, Dr Sherly Abraham. "Women in STEM & cyber security fields." American society for Engineering Education, 2014.
- G.Padmavathi, M.Uma &. "A Survey on various cyber attacks & their classification." 2011.
- Pilling, Rafe. "Global threats, cyber-security nightmares & how to protect against them." Elsevier ltd, 2013.
- Raytheon. "Securing our future: Closing the cyber security Talent Gap." 2016.
- S.Chai & S.bagchai- sen, C.Morrell, H.R.Rao & S.Upadhyaya. "Role of perceived importance of Information Security: An Exploratory study of Middle School Children's Information Security Behaviour." *Issues in Information Science & Information Technology*, 2006.
- Sangmi chai, Sharmistha Bagchi, Rajni goel, H.Raghav, Shambhu upadhyaya. "A Framework for understanding Minority students' Cyber security career interests." 2006.
- Sharmistha Bagchi-Sen, H.R.Rao, Shambhu J.Upadhyaya, Sangmi Chai. "Women in cybersecurity: A study of career advancement." ISSN, 2010.
- Yougal Joshi, Anand singh. "A Study on cyber crime and security scenario in INDIA." *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*, 2013.